

CRU TS3.24.01 Climatology Data for the IPCC DDC

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Summary

CRU TS3.24.01 (Harris et. al., 2014) monthly mean climatology data matching those used in IPCC WG1 AR5 (Stoker et. al., 2013) have been calculated at CEDA. The fields match those produced for AR4. The newly derived data will be available as netcdf data files and also as geotiff images.

Variables

The variables for which climatological data have been calculated are:

- cloud cover (clد)
- diurnal temperature range (dtr)
- ground frost frequency (frs)
- potential evapotranspiration (pet)
- precipitation (pre)
- near-surface temperature minimum (tmn)
- near-surface temperature (tmp)
- near-surface temperature maximum (tmx)
- vapour pressure (vap)
- wet day frequency (wet)

Time periods

The climatological data for CRU TS3.24.01 has been calculated with reference to 10- and 30-year period averages. The periods for which the climatologies have been calculated are listed below.

- decadal means: 1901-1910, 1911-1920, ..., 2001-2010
- thirty year means: 1901-1930, 1931-1960, 1961-1990

Output specification

Both anomalies and absolute values have been calculated.

Anomaly values are taken as anomalies from the 1986-2005 mean (baseline values).

Output

- Period mean of the monthly mean of the variables
- 12 monthly values per climatology
- Climatology is a 2D field
- One climatology per variable per time period
- CF compliant netCDF files
- GeoTIFF files (1 per month per variable per time period)

Directory structure

The root directory is `/derived/`.

Sub-directory is then `clim-anom-ref5/` for the anomalies and `clim/` for the absolute values. Sub-directories from these are `netcdf/` and `geotiff/` for the netCDF and GeoTIFF output respectively.

Each anomaly file has the extended attribute: `clim-anom-ref5`. This indicates that it is a climatological mean anomaly (`clim-anom`) and that the reference period matches the AR5 reference period (`ref5`).

Each absolute value file has the extended attribute `clim`, indicating it is a climatological mean.

Method

The algorithm for calculating the baseline climatologies and climatological anomalies follows the process below:

- For every variable (if available):
 - calculate the 1986-2005 climatological (period average) monthly means (baseline).
- For every time period:
 - For every variable (if available):
 - calculate the climatological monthly mean for this (time period, variable) and subtract from the relevant baseline.

Sensitivity experiments

To determine the effect that changing the reference period has on the results, a sensitivity analysis has been performed.

Here the climatological monthly means for the reference period used in AR5 (1986-2005) is subtracted from the climatological monthly means for the reference period used in AR4 (1961-1990).

This is performed on the CRU TS3.24.01 dataset for all variables.

These files are in the `sens/` directory and have the extended attribute `sens5-4`.

Code

The code for calculating the climatological baselines and anomalies can be found in the CEDA github repository https://github.com/cedadev/ipcc_ddc_cruts_clim_anoms.

References

Harris, I. and Jones, P.D. and Osborn, T.J. and Lister, D.H. (2014), Updated high-resolution grids of monthly climatic observations – the CRU TS3.10 Dataset, *International Journal of Climatology*, 34(3), 623--642, doi:10.1002/joc.3711

Stocker, T.F., D. Qin, G.-K. Plattner, M. Tignor, S.K. Allen, J. Boschung, A. Nauels, Y. Xia, V. Bex and P.M. Midgley (eds.) (2013), IPCC, 2013: *Climate Change 2013: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 1535 pp, doi:10.1017/CBO9781107415324.